

Erratum

The sentence after Eq. (2) should read:

The maximum measurable velocity can be increased by increasing the measurement angle α between the DOCT beam and the velocity vector.

Figure 3c and the paragraph related to Eq. (3) should be:

Figure 3 c) A closer look at the measurement optics. Here U is the real velocity, v is the component of velocity in the direction of the measurement beam, and n_f is the refractive index of the medium. Angle α is obtained by calculating first angle δ by applying the Snell's law of refraction to the two interfaces.

Figure 3 b shows as an example a measurement setup of pipe flow. From Figure 3 c, we get the real axial velocity in the pipe to be

$$U = \frac{v n_f}{\sin \beta}, \quad (1)$$

where β is the DOCT measurement angle (the angle between the camera axis and pipe surface normal), v is the velocity given by the DOCT device, and n_f is the refractive index of the monitored medium. Similar reasoning also works, e.g., for plate-plate and bob and cup rheometer geometries.